

Changes in urea N remaining at deep placement sites after application of SCU in a wetland soil. Ludhiana, India, 1988.

capacity/100 g. A nylon screen bag with 460 mg N as SCU (38.6% N) was placed between 2 layers of wet soil freshly collected from the lower layer of 3- × 5-cm or six 20- × 10 cm rice hills 5 d after transplanting of 45-d-old seedlings of cultivar PR106. The plots received a basal dose of 26 kg P and 50 kg K/ha. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design.

Five nylon bags from each treatment were chosen at random and SCU granules were digested, then analyzed for urea N at 6, 10, 25, 45, and 60 d after placement. The remaining wet soil mass was extracted with 2 M KCl-PMA solution, and the extract was also analyzed for urea N.

Results showed that SCU granules released urea N at a fairly controlled rate up to 60 d after placement. Spacing significantly affected the amounts of SCU N recovered. SCU N disappeared faster in the closer plant spacing (see figure). Closer plant spacing had more impact after 30 d of SCU placement, coinciding with active proliferation of rice roots. Furthermore, dissolution rate of SCU was about 9 and 19% higher than its empirical 7-d dissolution rate of 21% with 15- × 20-cm and 20- × 10-cm spacings, respectively. □

Effect of azolla and other fertilizers on rice yields

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We evaluated azolla as an organic manure, varying application rate and percentage of substitution for chemical fertilizer at RARS Pattambi during rabi seasons (Sep-Jan) of 1980 and 1981.

In the split-plot experiment, azolla at 5.0, 7.5, and 10.0 t/ha was compared with cattle manure and green leaves

(*Gliricidia maculata*) at 5 t/ha. Subplot treatment was the percentage of fertilizer dose (90:45:45 kg NPK/ha) applied. The sandy loam soil contained 0.02% available N, 9.7 kg available P, and 184.4 kg K with a pH of 5.5. On dry weight basis, cattle manure has 9.4% dry matter, 1.52% N, 0.4% P, and 21.1% K; for gliricidia, the values are 21.1, 2.6, 0.5, and 1.4%.

Substituting 5 t azolla/ha for cattle manure saved 25% of the fertilizer dose (see table). Azolla at 7.5 t/ha with full dose of fertilizer recorded the highest grain and straw yields. Applying more than 7.5 t azolla/ha was not beneficial. □

Effect of organic manures and fertilizer levels on grain yield of rice. Pattambi, India, 1980 and 1981 rabi (Sep-Jan).

Organic manure	Rate (t/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha) with given fertilizer dose ^a				
		0	25%	50%	75%	100%
Control	0	1.8	2.3	2.7	3.1	3.6
Cattle manure	5.0	2.4	2.7	3.1	3.1	3.6
Green leaves	5.0	2.8	3.1	3.4	3.6	3.8
Azolla	5.0	2.1	2.7	2.8	3.4	3.7
Azolla	7.5	2.6	3.0	3.2	3.7	4.2
Azolla	10.0	2.3	2.8	3.2	3.2	3.7
<i>F</i> test ^b		*				
LSD (0.05)		0.27 ^c	0.29 ^d			

^aFertilizer dose: 90-45-45 kg NPK/ha. ^bSignificant at 0.05 level. ^cFor comparing 2 fertilizer levels at the same level of organic manure. ^dFor comparing 2 organic manures at the same or different levels of fertilizer.

Effects of seedling age and zinc application on yield of rice

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We evaluated the impact of seedling age and Zn application on rice in wet season, using three seedling ages as main plots, five rates of Zn applied through soil and one foliar spray as subplots, with three replications (see table). Seedlings (30, 40, and 50 d old) of variety Pant Dhan 4 were transplanted at 2-3 seedlings/hill, 20- × 20-cm spacing. Soil was Beni silty clay loam, fine silty, mixed, hyperthermic, Aquic

Hapludoll with pH 7.6, CEC 20 meq/100 g, 1.0% organic C, 20 kg available (Olsen) P/ha, and 0.8 ppm Zn.

Grain yield declined significantly with increasing seedling age (see table). Panicles/m² and filled grains/panicle were significantly higher with 30- and 40-d-old seedlings than with 50-d-old ones. Filled grain percentage and 1,000-grain weight were significantly higher with 30- and 40-d-old seedlings than with 50-d-old ones.

Application of 8 ppm Zn gave significantly higher yield than other Zn treatments; 4 ppm Zn was significantly superior to Zn spray, 1 ppm Zn, and the control. Panicles/m², filled grains/panicle, and filled grains percentage were significantly higher with 8 ppm Zn than with all other

Yield and yield attributes of rice as affected by seedling age and rate of Zn application. Nainital, India, 1988 wet season.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	Filled grain percentage	1000-grain weight (g)
Seedling age (d)					
30	6.7	197	131	90.3	29.0
40	6.2	194	127	91.2	29.2
50	5.7	182	122	86.5	28.7
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.2	6	2	1.9	0.4
Zn rate (ppm)					
0	5.9	180	111	87.3	28.1
1	5.9	184	118	87.8	28.7
2	6.2	190	127	89.1	28.9
4	6.4	197	132	90.1	29.4
8	6.7	208	148	92.7	29.8
Spray	6.0	189	122	88.9	28.8
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.3	6	4	1.5	1.1

treatments, but 1,000-grain weight was not.

The interaction between seedling age and Zn rate was not significant. □

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Disease management

A new sheath disease of rice in India caused by *Monographella albescens*

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From Oct 1986 onward, we observed a severe sheath disease of rice in MAC experimental plots and in many farmers' fields.

The lesions develop as oblong or irregular spots 1-2 cm long and 0.5-1.0 cm wide with dark brown margins and greyish centers. About 80-100% of uppermost leaf sheaths enclosing young panicles are rotted. Many small, black, fruiting bodies (perithecia) of *M. albescens* appear on infected sheaths and grains.

We isolated the pathogen from fresh diseased specimen on potato dextrose agar. It produced white mycelium during early growth. At maturity, it produced pink patches of conidial masses. We inoculated the injured sheaths with conidial suspension prepared from a 7-d-old culture. Symptoms appeared 4 d after inoculation. In 2 wk, uppermost leaf sheaths and young panicles completely

rotted. Several superficial, black perithecia were formed.

Microscopic examination showed morphological characteristics exactly the same as those of leaf scald (LSc) pathogen. The anamorph and teleomorph have been identified as *Gerlachia oryzae* (Hashioka and

Yokogi), *W. Gams* and *M. albescens* (Thiimen) Parkinson, Sivanesan, and Booth, respectively. The anamorph of the LSc pathogen was previously reported in India, but the teleomorph has evidently not been. This indicates that the same fungus can produce different disease symptoms. □

Improved method of purifying rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV)

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We improved the method of purifying RTSV without using organic solvent and driselase:

Infected TN plants at 45-60 d

Harvest whole plants except roots.

Homogenize in 3 volumes of 0.01 M EDTA, pH 8.4.

Filter through cheesecloth.

Filtrate

Stir at room temperature for 2 h.

Incubate in water bath at 40 °C for 2 h.

15,000 g for 10 min.

Supernatant

Add PEG 8000 to 7%, NaCl to 0.2M and Triton X-100 to 1%.

Stir at room temperature for 1 h.

30,000 g for 30 min.

Pellet

Resuspend in 20 ml 0.01 M EDTA, pH 8.4.

11,000g for 10 min.

Supernatant

100,000 g for 60 min.

Pellet

Resuspend in 2 ml 0.01 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.2. 11,000 g for 10 min.

Supernatant

Layer on 10-50% linear sucrose density gradient in PB.

25,000 rpm for 2 h.

Collect a virus zone (ca. 3 cm below the meniscus).

Dilute with 0.01 PB.

130,000 g for 1 h.

Pellet

Resuspend in 2 ml 0.01 PB. 11,000 g for 10 min.

Supernatant (virus preparation)